

Mapping Research Topics on Sharia and Conventional Bank Jabar Banten (BJB): VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Bank Jabar Banten Sharia and Conventional. The research was conducted from 2011 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword " Bank Jabar Banten ". Based on the search results, there were 43 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Bank Jabar Banten is divided into 6 clusters and 122 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 5 main themes related to Bank Jabar Banten Sharia and Conventional.

Keywords: Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) Sharia and Conventional, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review

Introduction

The banking business in Indonesia is increasingly developing along with the public's understanding of interest (riba) because the majority of Indonesian people are Muslim. This is supported by the government which has issued Law Number 10 of 1998 concerning banking businesses which can carry out a dual banking system in running their business. This makes conventional banks that have expanded widely to start running sharia business units. Its implementation is accompanied by provisions contained in Law Number 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking which covers everything regarding institutions, business activities, and methods and processes for running banking businesses based on sharia principles.

The use of a dual banking system in Indonesian banking emerged from Law Number 10 of 1998 which is related to Law Number 21 of 2008, which regulates that developing sharia banks can be done by implementing a dual banking system or two banking systems simultaneously, namely the interest-based banking activities (conventional) and non-interest-based banking activities (syariah). This requires setting up the working mechanism if it is a dual system banking is applied especially in matters relating to interest-based activities which are characteristic of conventional banking with interest-free activities which are different from sharia banking. The establishment of Sharia Banks was supported by the desire of the Islamic community to avoid usury in their transactions. Thus, Bank BJB opened BJB Syariah as a solution for people who want to carry out transactions according to sharia principles. This is proven by research results which show the influence of knowledge about the mechanisms and principles of sharia banking products on the decision to become a customer at BJBS. This research also shows that there is a relationship between the motivation variable to avoid usury and knowledge of sharia banking products in making the decision to become a BJBS customer.

In previous research, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah (BJBS) continued to show positive growth in recent years. The following is some information about the development of BJBS, including: first, growth in assets and income. At the end of 2020, BJBS' total assets reached IDR. 16.34 trillion or an increase of 14.03%

compared to the previous year. Meanwhile, BJBS's revenue in 2020 reached IDR. 1.2 trillion or an increase of 16.91% compared to the previous year. Second, branch office expansion. BJBS also continues to expand branch offices in various regions in Indonesia. At the end of 2020, BJBS had a total of 103 branch offices spread across 15 provinces in Indonesia. Third, improving Digital Services. BJBS also continues to strive to improve digital services to make it easier for customers to carry out transactions. In 2020, BJBS launched a mobile banking application that allows customers to carry out banking transactions online. Fourth, improving Financial Performance. In recent years, BJBS has succeeded in recording positive financial performance growth. In 2020, BJBS managed to record a net profit of IDR. 196.98 billion or an increase of 42.47% compared to the previous year. Overall, BJBS's development in recent years shows positive and consistent growth in financial aspects, branch expansion and digital services. This shows that BJBS continues to strive to become one of the leading sharia banks in Indonesia.

In 2020, BJB recorded an increase in net profit of 5.5% compared to the previous year, even though interest income fell 8.4% due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. In September 2021, BJB also announced plans to strengthen capital by issuing bonds worth IDR 1 trillion (around US\$ 70 million) to support future business growth. Apart from that, BJB also continues to improve its digital services, including the launch of a mobile banking application in 2020 and the development of technology-based banking services such as BJB Digi and BJB Smart. This helps BJB to continue to compete with other banks in Indonesia and makes it easy for customers to access banking services.

Based on a search on the Garuda web site (Digital Reference Garba), there are 30 studies about Bank Jabar Banten Syariah. Apart from that, there are 50 studies on conventional Bank Jabar Banten until 2022. However, these two banks also experience instability in their annual publications. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out further studies regarding this matter. This research aims to obtain an overview of the development of research related to Bank Jabar Banten for 11 years, namely from 2011 to 2022, using the method bibliometrics VOSviewer and literature review studies.

Literature Review

The establishment of Bank BJB Syariah began with the formation of the Sharia Division by PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Barat and Banten Tbk on May 20 2000. The aim of establishing the Sharia Division was to meet the needs of the people of West Java who had a great interest in using sharia banking services at that time. That. After the General Meeting of Shareholders (GMS) of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Barat and Banten Tbk was held and approved, the Sharia Division was changed to a Sharia Commercial Bank or what is now known as BJB Syariah.

Bibliometry k is a method that refers to the mathematical and statistical analysis related to the publication and use of documents. Bibliometry k can be defined as the analysis of citations and number of publications. The publications or documents in question are not limited to specific works, but can also include electronic journals, voice messages, and video images.

VOS viewer is software used to create maps based on metadata, and has functions for visualizing and exploring map data. According to Eck and Waltman in their book in 2022, VOSviewer is divided into two main functions, namely: first, creating maps based on network data by displaying network visualizations related to the publication of scientific papers, scientific journals, researchers, research organizations, countries of origin, even words. keys connected to co-authorship, cooccurrence, citation, bibliographic coupling, or co-citation links used as input in VOSviewer. Second, provide visualization and explore the map. VOSviewer also

provides visualizations from maps, networks, to overlays, as well as density or sparseness visualization of network data by exploring the complete details of the metadata.

Literature reviews or literature reviews play a very important role in many types of research, because they function to provide an understanding of the development of knowledge, as a reference that can provide stimulus in policy making, search for new ideas, and as a guide in the field of research. Therefore, it can be concluded that Literature Review is a research method that aims to collect the essence of the research that has been carried out, put it together, and analyze the overview from experts.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) Sharia and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Jabar Banten " for the entire year period (2011 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) Sharia and Conventional

Based on a search of scientific publications about Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) from 2011 to 2022, there are 46 research articles discussing this topic and published in accredited national journals. The most publications occurred in 2019, namely 8 research publications. The average publication each year is 3 published articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data about Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2011	1	2015	4	2019	8
2012	3	2016	5	2020	4
2013	5	2017	5	2021	4
2014	2	2018	2	2022	5
Total = 43					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

There are seven institutions that publish research articles about Bank Jabar Banten (BJB). These institutions are the Journal of Financial and Banking Science (JIKA) from the Department of Business Administration, FISIP, Diponegoro University, and the Syari'ah Economics Journal from the Faculty of Islamic Economics and Business, Darussalam Islamic Institute (IAID) Ciamis, West Java, Indonesia. Each of these institutions published three articles.

Table 2. Journal of publishers of scientific publications about Banten Network (BJB)

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Finance and Banking Science (JIKA), Syari'ah Economics	3
Al-Amwal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Journal of Business and Economic Accounting, Ranggagading Scientific Journal of Accounting and Management, Journal of Accounting and Sharia Business (AKSY), Garut University Communication Journal: Results of Thought and Research	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The authors of all research articles published on the Garuda website have each published only 1 research article regarding sharia and conventional BJB, here are the names of the authors:

Table 3. Author of scientific articles about Bank Jabar Banten (BJB)

Researcher Name	Affiliate
Sutarti, Enjang Tachyan Budianto, Abdillah Saesar, Annaria Magdalena Marpaung, Siti Ita Rosita	STIE Unity
Adnan Sharif, Abdul Kohar Irwanto, Tubagus Nur Ahmad Maulana	Department and Master of Management, FEM IPB
Wartoyo	IAIN Sheikh Nurjati Cirebon
Rahmawati Dwina Putri, Dian Hakip Nurdiansyah	Singaperbangsa University Karawang
Nurlaelah Zakiah, Ilis Solehah, Lilis Sulastri, Lenny Yanthiani, Usep Deden Suherman, Sidiq Permana, Yusuf Ajazy	Sunan Gunung Djati State Islamic University, Bandung
Adelia Sarimukti, Dedi Suselo	UIN Sayyid Ali Rahmatullah
Alvin Cakra Pratista	Bandung Islamic University
Rosa Fitriana, Susi Octaviyanti	Bale University Bandung
Asti Marlina	Ibn Khaldun University
Azizah Indriyani	Muhadi Setiabudi University
Laili Rahmawati	STEBI Al Jabar Bandung
Ana Herlina, Dede Husni Mubarak, Helmi Maulana, Eka Fitria, Sumadi, Eggy Armand Ramdani, Tiara Ramadanti	Darussalam Islamic Institute (IAID), Ciamis, West Java
Nina Febriani Nurjanah	UIN SGD Bandung
Sylvia Rozza, Muchtasib, Ach. Bakhrul	Jakarta State Polytechnic
Muhammad Iqbal Nugraha	Langlangbuana University Bandung
Dian Anita	Bandung Business School
Dasrun Hidayat	Adhirajasa Reswara Sanjaya University

Didin Rasyidin Wahyu	Bina Bangsa University
Arman Maulana	Nusantara Islamic University
Ade Nawawi, Pitriani	Subang University
Siti Rosmayati, Elis Esye	STIE Equity Bandung
Dini Istihana, Yati Mulyati	Widyatama University
Ine Anggraeni	Garut University
Heni Mulyani	Semarang State University
Caecilia Sri Wahyuning, Yuniar	Bandung National Institute of Technology
Kartika Nurhayati, Ari Pradhanawati, Andi Wijayanto	Diponegoro University
Donni June Priansa	AMIK BSI Bandung
Thyophoida WS Panjaitan	Darma Cendika Catholic University
David Viansyah, Rizki Zulfikar, Akmal Faiz Prasetyo, Lazuardi, Aldi Rahman, Raras Anggono, Yoyo Sudaryo, Marismiati, Askia Esa Aulia, Empung, Indra Mahdi, Itsnaini Khairunnisa, Layaman, Novi Andriyani, Agia Dwi Vici Utami, Suci Nujiana, Mega Mutia Maeskina, Sri Dinarwati, Zikri Fachrul Nurhadi, Hendi Rohendi, Anggi Pasca Arnu, M. Taufik Aziz, Fitri Rayanti, Nana Darna, Sniar Budiarti, Adam Adiwiguna, Mila Julyani Hernama, Oman Suryaman, Yoni Budiman, Bertha Musty, Yuli Anwar	Unknown Affiliation

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping Research Regarding Bank Jabar Banten (BJB) Sharia and Conventional

Research articles obtained from search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) which are then downloaded in the form of RIS (Research Information Systems) which are then input into the software VOSViewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Sharia and Conventional Bank Jabar Banten (BJB)

Mapping Literature Review regarding Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Sharia and Conventional Products

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 6 selected products from Bank Jabar Banten, namely:

First, the Employee Welfare Financing/PKP product uses a Murabahah contract. This is a sharia financing product offered by banks to help meet employees' financial needs. This financing uses a Murabahah contract, which is a form of buying and selling transaction with profits disclosed openly. In this case, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will buy goods that employees want, such as cars or electronic goods, then resell these goods to employees at a higher price. The benefits of this transaction will be clearly disclosed to employees. The way this financing works is as follows: (1) Employees submit a financing application to Bank Jabar Banten Syariah by including the required documents; (2) Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will evaluate the application and determine whether the application is approved or not; (3) If the application is approved, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will purchase the goods desired by the employee; (4) After that, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will resell the goods to employees at a higher price in accordance with the agreement; (5) The employee will pay the price in installments over a previously agreed period; and (6) After all installment payments have been made, the employee will become the owner of the goods purchased. This Employee Welfare Financing (PKP) product is designed to help meet employee financial needs in an easy and sharia way. By using a Murabahah contract, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah provides clear benefits to employees and avoids the element of usury in financing transactions.

Second, the main microcredit products. The main micro credit products offered by Bank Jabar Banten are as follows:

- (1) People's Business Credit (KUR), which is a micro credit product provided by the government to help Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in developing their businesses. Bank Jabar Banten provides KUR with low interest and flexible terms.
- (2) Business Micro Credit, namely a micro credit product intended for MSMEs that require working capital or investment in order to improve their business. This product has a credit period that can be adjusted to customer needs.
- (3) Unsecured Micro Credit (KMTA), which is a micro credit product provided to MSME customers who do not have collateral to use as collateral. This product has low interest and flexible credit terms.
- (4) Unsecured Micro Credit (KMTJ), namely a micro credit product provided to MSME customers who do not have collateral but have good business potential. This product has competitive interest and a credit term that can be adjusted to customer needs.
- (5) Business Development Micro Credit (KMBU), which is a micro credit product intended for MSME customers who want to start or develop their business. This product has low interest and a credit term that can be adjusted to customer needs.

Third, the Guna Bhakti credit fund product. The Guna Bhakti credit fund product at Bank Jabar Banten is a credit product provided by the bank to customers who need funds for consumptive or productive purposes. The following is some information regarding Guna Bhakti credit products at Bank Jabar Banten: (1) Guna Bhakti Credit is available in various types of credit, such as Multipurpose Credit, Education Credit, Home Renovation Credit, Working Capital Credit, and Investment Credit; (2) The Guna Bhakti Credit period at Bank Jabar Banten can be adjusted to suit customer needs, starting from 12 months to 120 months (10 years); (3) The amount of credit that a customer can apply for depends on the type of credit chosen. The minimum credit amount is IDR 5 million and the maximum can reach IDR 2 billion; (4) Required documents that must be provided to apply for Guna Bhakti

Credit include photocopies of KTP, NPWP, income statement, checking or savings account, and other necessary supporting documents; (5) The interest rate applied to Guna Bhakti Credit depends on the type of credit and term. Interest rates may change according to Bank Jabar Banten policy; and (6) The administration fee charged for Guna Bhakti Credit is 1-2% of the amount of credit applied for. With this Guna Bhakti Credit product, Bank Jabar Banten provides financial solutions for customers who need funds for various purposes. However, before applying for credit, make sure you understand all the applicable terms and conditions and consider your ability to pay off credit installments regularly.

Fourth, home ownership financing products. The home ownership financing product at Bank Jabar Banten is one type of credit product provided by this bank to help people who want to own a house. This product is called Bank Jabar Banten Home Ownership Credit (KPR). Some of the advantages of Bank Jabar Banten's mortgage products include: (1) Credit with low interest rates, so monthly installments are more affordable; (2) Flexible in the choice of term, starting from 1 to 20 years, according to the customer's abilities and needs; (3) Fast and easy credit approval process, and requirements that are relatively easy to fulfill; (4) There are several types of KPR programs provided by Bank Jabar Banten, such as Sharia KPR and Subsidized KPR. Apart from that, Bank Jabar Banten also offers other programs that can help customers meet their home financing needs, such as home renovation or development programs, as well as refinancing programs. However, before applying for a KPR, customers must pay attention to several important things, such as the ability to pay the installments, the amount of the down payment that must be prepared, and other costs related to the KPR application process. Make sure to make careful calculations and choose a mortgage product that suits your needs and financial capabilities.

Fifth, capital loans from the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative/KJKS. Bank Jabar Banten Syariah capital loans to the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) can be carried out in several stages as follows: (1) Preparation of documents and requirements, namely before applying for a capital loan at Bank Jabar Banten Syariah, KJKS must prepare the required documents and requirements, such as business permits, financial reports, and other legal documents; (2) Submitting a loan application, namely after the documents and requirements have been prepared, KJKS can submit a capital loan application to Bank Jabar Banten Syariah via the form provided; (3) Evaluation of loan feasibility, namely Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will evaluate the feasibility of capital loans proposed by KJKS, including financial and risk analysis; (4) Determination of the loan amount, namely if KJKS is declared worthy of obtaining a capital loan, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will determine the amount of the loan to be provided, in accordance with the KJKS' needs and capabilities; (5) Disbursement of funds, namely after the loan amount is determined, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah will disburse the funds to KJKS. The loan amount will be paid in installments over the previously agreed term and interest; and (6) Loan repayment, namely KJKS is obliged to pay off the capital loan in accordance with the agreement agreed with Bank Jabar Banten Syariah. If KJKS is unable to pay the loan according to the predetermined schedule, it will be subject to sanctions and fines according to applicable regulations.

Sixth, Wadiah contract on IB Maslahah savings. The Wadiah contract product for IB Maslahah savings at Bank Jabar Banten Syariah is a type of sharia savings product that is based on the Wadiah principle, namely a contract that requires the bank to safeguard and manage customer funds stored in the bank as well as possible. In the IB Maslahah savings product at Bank Jabar Banten Syariah, customers deposit funds into a savings account provided by the bank using a Wadiah contract. As a deposit-taking bank, Bank Jabar Banten Syariah is responsible for maintaining security and managing customer funds well. Benefits for customers who

use the Wadiah contract product for IB Maslahah savings at Bank Jabar Banten Syariah include, savings funds will receive a guarantee of safety and security in their management, customers can also enjoy different levels of profit depending on the interest rate applicable to the savings product the sharia.

4. Mapping Literature Review regarding the Financial Performance of Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Sharia and Conventional

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 11 BJB financial performance reports, namely:

First, the influence of Debt Financing and Equity Financing on the Profit Expense Ratio. The effect of Debt Financing on PER at Bank Jabar Banten can vary depending on how much interest expense must be paid. If a bank borrows funds at low interest, the effect on PER will be positive, because the bank can use the funds obtained to increase income and generate greater profits. However, if the interest that must be paid is high, it will have a negative influence on PER, because high interest expenses will reduce the bank's net income. The effect of Equity Financing on PER at Bank Jabar Banten can be positive, because by having sufficient capital, the bank can increase income by making larger investments. Apart from that, by having strong capital owners, banks will also be more trusted by customers and investors, thereby increasing their reputation and number of customers. However, keep in mind that selling shares can reduce the bank's ownership by the owner, so the owner must share the profits with the new shareholders.

Second, the influence of PSAK 101 on the fairness of financial statement presentation. Bank Jabar Banten will have to follow the provisions stated in PSAK 101 to ensure that the financial reports presented are in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles. This aims to ensure that the financial reports presented can be trusted by parties who use the information, such as investors, creditors, regulators and other stakeholders. Several things that can be influenced by PSAK 101 on the fairness of the presentation of financial reports at Bank Jabar Banten include: (1) Presentation of financial information that is more transparent and structured; (2) Present complete and accurate financial information; (3) Ensure proper recognition of revenues and expenses in the relevant period; (4) Present information about assets, liabilities and equity clearly and completely; and (5) Present clear and complete information about cash flows.

Third, the influence of PSAK 107 on gold pawning products. The influence of PSAK 107 on gold pawning products at Bank Jabar Banten Syariah can be seen from several aspects, including:

- (1) Recognition and measurement. PSAK 107 requires Bank Jabar Banten Syariah to recognize gold pawn products as part of its assets and measure them in a manner that complies with sharia accounting principles. This affects the way banks manage and process gold pawn transactions.
- (2) Financial statements. PSAK 107 regulates the presentation of transparent and accurate financial reports. Bank Jabar Banten Syariah must present information regarding gold pawning products in its financial reports clearly and in detail, so that stakeholders can properly understand the bank's financial position.
- (3) Sharia compliance. PSAK 107 encourages Bank Jabar Banten Syariah to run gold pawn products in accordance with sharia accounting principles and sharia principles in general. This affects the bank's compliance with sharia rules and can increase customer confidence in the gold pawn products offered.

Fourth, the influence of PSAK 105 on the accounting treatment of Mudharabah funding. In PSAK 105, there are several requirements that must be fulfilled by sharia banks in accounting for Mudharabah funding. Some of these requirements include: (1) Mudharabah financing must be treated as a contract between the bank and the customer and must be properly documented; (2) Banks

must identify and separate each type of financing provided and record it separately; (3) Banks must record expenses related to Mudharabah financing and allocate expenses in accordance with the agreed profit sharing principles.

Fifth, the influence of Operational Expenses on Operational Income/BOPO, credit quality, capital adequacy, interest income, Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing, profit sharing expenses, credit risk, Non-Performing Financing/NPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Current Asset Saving Account/CASA, Fee Based Income/FCB, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR to Return On Assets/ROA

Sixth, the influence of credit quality which is classified as unproductive in the construction sector on the level of bank credit soundness. The quality of credit classified as unproductive in the construction sector can have a significant influence on the credit health level of Bank Jabar Banten. For example, if Bank Jabar Banten has many loans given to construction companies which then fail to pay back the loans, then this will affect the credit quality and the bank's credit health level. In this case, credit quality that is classified as unproductive can indicate high credit risk. This credit risk can occur because construction companies may experience financial problems that make them unable to repay the loan. If Bank Jabar Banten has a lot of credit that is classified as unproductive in the construction sector, then this could affect the bank's ability to provide new loans in the future. In addition, Bank Jabar Banten may also need to take action to collect unpaid loans, which can be time consuming and costly. To overcome this risk, Bank Jabar Banten can carry out better credit risk management and diversify their credit portfolio to reduce the risk of concentration in the construction sector. Bank Jabar Banten can also tighten loan requirements for construction companies or carry out a more careful risk analysis before providing loans to the construction sector.

Seventh, Liquidity risk, including: Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. Several factors that can influence Bank Jabar Banten's liquidity risk include:

- (1) Customer Fund Withdrawal Patterns. If large amounts of customer funds are withdrawn at once, the bank must be able to fulfill the request quickly without experiencing liquidity difficulties. Therefore, Bank Jabar Banten needs to pay attention to customer fund withdrawal patterns to anticipate liquidity risks.
- (2) Asset Quality. Poor asset quality can impact a bank's liquidity, as the bank may need to sell these assets to meet payment obligations. Therefore, Bank Jabar Banten needs to ensure that its assets are of good quality.
- (3) Liquidity Policy. Bank Jabar Banten needs to have a clear and measurable liquidity policy to manage its liquidity risk. This policy may include the amount of liquidity reserves that must be maintained, funding sources, and liquidity risk tolerance limits.
- (4) Financial Market Conditions. Financial market conditions can affect bank liquidity, especially if a financial crisis occurs. Therefore, Bank Jabar Banten needs to monitor financial market conditions and have a strategy to face possible bad scenarios.

Eighth, profitability risk, includes: Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Operational Expenses to Operating Income/BOPO. Several factors that can influence bank profitability risk include: (1) Interest rates, that is, if interest rates fall, the interest margin generated by the bank will also decrease, which can affect the bank's profitability; (2) Asset quality, namely if the quality of the bank's assets is poor, the bank can experience significant losses, which can affect its profitability; (3) Industrial competition, namely intense competition in the banking industry which can reduce the profit margins generated by banks; and (4) Changes in regulations, namely changes in regulations can affect bank operations and costs, which in turn can affect its profitability.

Ninth, Solvency ratio, includes: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. Solvency risk at Bank Jabar Banten is related to the bank's ability to fulfill its long-term financial obligations, including obligations to its customers. If the bank experiences difficulty in fulfilling these obligations, there will be a risk of inability or bankruptcy. Several factors that can influence Bank Jabar Banten's solvency risk include: (1) Solvency risk can increase if the bank has bad or illiquid assets that are difficult to sell or use as collateral for loans; (2) If bank capital is insufficient to cover possible losses, then solvency risk may increase; (3) Solvency risk may increase if bank management cannot carry out operations effectively and efficiently, or if there is fraud and legal violations; (4) Solvency risk may increase if poor economic and financial market conditions cause a decrease in asset values or an increase in interest rates, thereby worsening the bank's financial position.

Tenth, the influence of inflation, GDP, DPK, and FDR on problematic financing. Here are some ways in which each factor can influence problematic financing:

- (1) Inflation: A high inflation rate can affect problematic financing at Bank Jabar Banten by increasing operational costs and credit risk. High inflation can increase raw material costs, labor costs and other operational costs, which in turn can increase the company's financial burden. In addition, inflation can also affect consumers' ability to repay loans, thereby increasing credit risk.
- (2) GDP: Low or stagnant economic growth can affect financing problems at Bank Jabar Banten by reducing income and consumers' ability to repay loans. Slow economic growth can also affect a company's earnings and overall financial performance, which in turn can increase credit risk.
- (3) DPK: A low level of DPK (Third Party Funds) can affect financing problems at Bank Jabar Banten by reducing sources of funds for providing loans. Low deposits can make it difficult for banks to provide new financing and maintain existing financing, which in turn can increase credit risk.
- (4) FDR: A high FDR (Fund Deposit Ratio) level can affect problematic financing at Bank Jabar Banten by reducing bank liquidity. A high FDR can make a bank less liquid, making it difficult to meet customer funding needs and provide new financing. This can increase credit risk and worsen financing problems.

Eleventh, the influence of the competence and independence of internal auditors on the quality of audit results. In general, the competence and independence of internal auditors can have a positive influence on the quality of audit results in an organization, including Bank Jabar Banten. The following is a more detailed explanation regarding the influence of each of these factors: (1) Competence of internal auditors. Internal auditor competency can be interpreted as the ability or expertise possessed by an internal auditor in carrying out his duties. In this case, the higher the level of competency of the internal auditor at Bank Jabar Banten, the better the quality of the audit results produced. Competent internal auditors will be able to carry out careful analysis and evaluation of financial reports and business processes at Bank Jabar Banten. Apart from that, they are also able to identify risks that may occur and provide recommendations to reduce these risks. In this way, the resulting examination results will be more accurate and can help Bank Jabar Banten management in making the right decisions. (2) Independence of internal auditors. Internal auditor independence can be interpreted as the ability of an internal auditor to carry out his duties objectively and not be influenced by other parties who can influence the results of the audit. In this case, the higher the level of independence of the internal auditors at Bank Jabar Banten, the better the quality of the audit results produced. An independent internal auditor will be able to carry out audits objectively and not be influenced by the interests of any party, including the management of Bank Jabar Banten. In this way, the resulting examination results

will be more accurate and can provide greater benefits for Bank Jabar Banten. In conclusion, both the competence and independence of internal auditors have a very important influence on the quality of audit results at Bank Jabar Banten. The higher the level of competence and independence of internal auditors at Bank Jabar Banten, the better the quality of the audit results produced. Therefore, Bank Jabar Banten needs to pay attention to and improve the quality of competence and independence of its internal auditors in order to improve the quality of the audit results produced.

Literature Review Mapping regarding Innovations Implemented by Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Sharia and Conventional

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 3 innovations carried out by BJB, namely:

First, the strategy for optimizing the financing risk management system. Several general strategies that can help in optimizing the bank's financing risk management system:

- (1) Risk Identification: Identify the types of risks that may occur in financing, such as credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk and operational risk. After risk identification is carried out, an assessment of the impact and probability of the risk occurring is then carried out.
- (2) Risk Measurement: Using risk measurement methods that are appropriate to the type of risk previously identified. For example, if credit risk is the most significant risk, then the bank can use credit risk measurement methods such as Value at Risk (VaR) or Expected Loss (EL).
- (3) Risk Mitigation: Taking action to reduce or eliminate identified risks, such as reducing risk exposure through portfolio diversification, improving internal supervision and control, or implementing a more effective risk management system.
- (4) Monitoring and Evaluation: Continuously monitor risks and evaluate the effectiveness of implemented risk mitigation strategies. This is important to ensure that the risk management system is continuously updated and adapted to changes in the business and regulatory environment.
- (5) Training and Development: Ensure that all staff are involved in the risk management process, understand the risks associated with their work, and have the necessary skills and knowledge to identify, measure and manage risks.

Second, analyze financial performance using the CAMEL method. The following are steps that can be taken to analyze the financial performance of Bank Jabar Banten using the CAMEL method. Capital Adequacy, namely the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is used to measure a bank's ability to meet the minimum capital requirements set by the bank supervisory authority. To calculate CAR, data is needed regarding total bank capital (including core capital and tier 2 capital) and total bank assets. Asset Quality, namely the NPL (Non-Performing Loan) ratio is used to measure the quality of credit owned by a bank. NPL is a loan that is past due and has not been repaid by the customer. To calculate the NPL ratio, data is needed regarding total NPL and total loans. Management, namely bank management is used to measure the quality of bank management in managing risks and overall bank operations. Several factors that need to be considered in this analysis are risk management policies, credit portfolio diversification, operational efficiency and corporate governance. Earnings, namely to measure a bank's financial performance, it is necessary to pay attention to profitability ratios such as Return On Assets (ROA) and Return On Equity (ROE). ROA measures the bank's ability to generate profits from total assets, while ROE measures the bank's ability to generate profits from shareholder capital. Liquidity, namely the Liquidity Ratio, is used to measure the bank's ability to fulfill financial obligations in the short term. Some liquidity ratios

that need to be considered are LDR (Loan to Deposit Ratio), LCR (Liquidity Coverage Ratio), and NSFR (Net Stable Funding Ratio).

Third, Customer Service communication patterns during the Covid-19 pandemic. Several practices carried out by Bank Jabar Banten during the Covid-19 pandemic to strengthen Customer Service communication patterns are:

- (1) Increasing the Availability of Online Services: Bank Jabar Banten can increase the availability of online banking services through a website or mobile banking application that is easy to access and user-friendly. In this case, customers can access information about their accounts, carry out banking transactions, and contact customer service from the comfort of their own homes.
- (2) Improving Online Customer Support: Apart from that, Bank Jabar Banten can improve online customer support via chat or instant messaging, email, or social media. Customers can ask questions about products and services, get technical assistance, or raise complaints or problems through this online medium.
- (3) Arranging the Customer Service Team's Work Schedule: Bank Jabar Banten can also arrange the customer service team's work schedule by paying attention to health protocols, such as limiting social distance and using masks. This allows customer service to operate safely and effectively.
- (4) Increase Response Speed: During the pandemic, customers may need help from customer service more often than usual. Bank Jabar Banten can increase the speed of customer service response through a system of assigning queue numbers or increasing the number of customer service staff.
- (5) Maintain Clear Communication: Lastly, it is important to maintain clear communication with customers during the pandemic. Bank Jabar Banten can provide clear and up-to-date information about bank policies relating to Covid-19, including changes to working hours or services available.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinants of Employee Work Motivation and Customer Interest in Saving at Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Sharia and Conventional

The first finding, based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, is that there are 9 determinants of BJB employee work motivation, namely: (1) Compensation; (2) Motivation; (3) Minimizing work stress in Back Office workers based on Galvanic Skin Response, Visual Analog Scale, and NIOSH General Job Stress Questionnaire; (4) Company culture; (5) Work environment; (6) Work productivity; (7) Leadership communication; (8) Competence; and (9) Organizational commitment.

The second finding, based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 18 determinants of BJB customer interest and satisfaction, namely: (1) Information technology; (2) Location; (3) Service quality using the service quality method and Kano diagram; (4) Religiosity; (5) Reputation; (6) Promotion; (7) Deposit interest rates; (8) ATM Services; (9) Brand equity; (10) Tangibles; (11) Reliability; (12) Responsiveness; (13) Guarantee; (14) Empathy; (15) Digital Marketing; (16) Supporting data; (17) Financial performance information; and (18) Marketing strategy.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Sharia and Conventional during the period 2011 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 43 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.

- The affiliates/institutions that publish the most research results are Finance and Banking Science (JIKA) from the Department of Business Administration, FISIP, Diponegoro University, and the Syari'ah Economics Journal from the Faculty of Islamic Economics and Business, Darussalam Islamic Institute (IAID) Ciamis, West Java, Indonesia. Each of these institutions published three articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Sharia and Conventional are divided into 6 clusters and 122 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 27 topics, cluster 2 consists of 22 topics, cluster 3 consists of 20 topics, cluster 4 consists of 18 topics, cluster 5 consists of 18 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 17 topics.
- Based on the literature review, there are 5 main research themes, namely : (1) Bank products; (2) Bank financial performance; (3) Innovation carried out by banks; (4) Determinants of bank employee work motivation; and (5) Determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in saving at the bank.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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